

**JUSTIFICATION OF THE STAGES OF TREATMENT WITH A RELAXING SPLINT IN
ACCORDANCE WITH THE DYNAMICS OF CLINICAL SYMPTOMS**

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Abstract

In modern dentistry, various methods have been developed to relieve symptoms by muscle tension in the maxillofacial region associated with changes in the spatial position of the lower jaw. Recently, there have been widespread recommendations on the use of relaxing splints to harmonize the neuromuscular activity of the motor component of the masticatory apparatus.

Keywords: relaxing splint, vertical splint, occlusal disorders, retrusion control, muscles of the maxillofacial region

According to the results of literary sources, occlusal splints (disconnectors, relaxing, stabilizing) are used from one month to several years [3, 4, 6]. In studies by Viveli C. et al., 2009, patients were followed up for 90 days after the splint was placed, and the state of muscle relaxation was corrected [5, 9, 10]. Unfortunately, today, despite the wide variety of proposed methods recommended for changing the spatial position of the lower jaw and a significant amount of scientific research in this direction, there is no single view on the timing of the use of splints in order to relax the muscles of the maxillofacial area and there is no control algorithm dynamics of treatment for their help [1,2,3]. Stages of treatment with a relaxing splint with retrusion control of signs of changes in occlusal contacts and elimination of symptoms of masticatory muscle soreness on palpation in persons with functional disorders against the background of generalized increased tooth abrasion. To accomplish the tasks set, 16 people (10 women, 6 men) with occlusal disorders due to the generation of an alized form of increased tooth abrasion, who applied for treatment at the NMU Dental Medical Center, were treated using relaxing splints. The average age of the persons was 39.3 ± 13.4 years.

The study included individuals with generalized increased tooth wear of I-III degrees and continuous dentition. The study excluded patients with defects in the dentition of medium and large size, with the presence of removable dentures and large bridges. The study was conducted with the permission of the Bioethical Committee of the National Medical University. The examination of patients was carried out according to the generally accepted scheme of the medical history (No. 043/o) using the algorithm of the clinical study of

muscles [8]. For the purpose of muscle relaxation, spatial positioning and stabilization of the lower jaw, taking into account the required bite height, patients were treated with a relaxing splint with retrusion control (Fig. 1). Splints were made in the articulator on models matched in the reference position, additional correction of the splint surface was carried out immediately after installation. Subsequently, occlusal correction of the splint occurred within 3, 7, 14 days and 1, 2, 3 months. These terms are chosen according to the physiological mechanisms of the processes of adaptation of the human body to prostheses [9]. It was also controlled that the surface of the tire remained flat after the correction. The contacts of the anterior teeth were removed. Within one month, the splint was remodeled in the frontal area to create an anterior guide for working out the functional movements of the lower jaw. In the second month of treatment, retrusion guiding slopes were created in the area of the premolars to block the distal displacement of the lower jaw - retrusion control.

The assessment of the state of masticatory muscles was carried out taking into account individual sensitivity to pain [3, 8]. and deep), lateral pterygoid (upper head, lower head), bigastric (anterior belly), maxillohyoid, medial pterygoid. Palpation of the muscles was carried out by ustra before splinting 3, 7, 14 days and 1, 2 and 3 months of using the splint before correcting the occlusal contacts on the splint. v.22. When comparing quantitative indicators, the method of analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used - in the case of a normal distribution law or a non-parametric analogue (Kruskal-Wallis criterion) - in the case of a difference between the separation law and the normal one. When comparing qualitative features, the Chi-square test was

used. Correlation analysis methods were used to analyze the presence of a statistical relationship between the signs.

The critical significance level in all cases was taken as $\alpha = 0.05$. During the first month of observation, a constant change in occlusal contacts was observed on the flat tire. The dynamics of changes in the number of contacts of antagonist teeth on the splint on the 3rd, 7th and 14th days and their non-physiological localization (frontal section of the splint, frontal-lateral one-sided location) were determined. At one month, significant changes in occlusal contacts were still observed, but this figure probably decreased ($p < 0.05$). Within two months, in 9 (56.25%) contact persons, the tires were defined as symmetrical and stable, in 7 people (43.75%), unwanted contacts were detected and their minor correction was carried out, after which the correction indicator decreased with a high degree of probability ($p < 0.01$). Within three months, one (6.25%) person underwent correction of contacts with significant statistically significant differences in indicators compared to the start of treatment ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1, Fig. 2). First of all, it is necessary to determine the predominant number of symptoms of muscles that lower the lower jaw and perform protrusion-retrusion positioning (44 (59.5%) symptoms) compared with the mandibular lifters in the observation group (30 (40.5%) symptoms).

The results of muscle palpation in patients in terms of 3, 7 and 14 days determined a decrease in the prevalence of pain symptoms and their tension by 22 (29.7%) signs. During the observation period of one month, a decrease in muscle tension was observed in 45 (60.8%) signs of the total number of symptoms. At the second month, the frequency of muscle symptoms decreased by 58 (78.4%) signs. Within a period of three months, a decrease in the manifestations of muscle symptoms by 69 (93.2%) signs was determined. Analysis of the muscles by function showed that during the first month the condition of the lifts of the lower slit improved significantly and the frequency of symptoms decreased by six times during the month of treatment, and later in the period of three months this indicator decreased to 100%. The state of the muscles that perform the protrusion-retrusion function and lower jaw depressors normalized much more slowly. Within one month, there was a decrease in the frequency of symptoms by 20 signs compared with the start of treatment (44 signs), which is 45.5%. Within three months, symptoms decreased to the level of 39 (88.6%) signs. Symptoms were determined in the hyoid muscles and may be related to the parafunction of the tongue, contacts and the total number of symptoms of soreness of the muscles of the maxillofacial area during palpation during three months of observation, a direct strong correlation was revealed ($\rho = 0.884$). The features of localization of contacts are determined and can be compared with the current relaxation of the masticatory muscle of the observation line. The results obtained confirm the data of scientific sources on changes in occlusal contacts during splint treatment [5, 1]. days does not change significantly ($p > 0.05$). Significant changes are determined a month after the start of treatment, which has solid scientific confirmation in numerous studies of neuromuscular regulation [2, 4]. the need for tire correction within the proposed time frame and coincides with the

conclusions of scientific sources [9, 10]. In our opinion, the absence or untimely control of occlusal contacts can lead to habituation, a forced open position of the lower jaw and increased discoordination of the interaction of the chewing apparatus components. patients with occlusal disorders. A device that provides relaxation of the masticatory muscles and creates a comfortable jaw closure pattern for the lower jaw can be used to register and transfer the therapeutic position of the lower jaw to the articulator at the stage of occlusion reorganization.

Correction of occlusal contacts on a relaxing occlusal splint should be carried out on time: 3, 7, 14 days and 1, 2 months and completed in three months. Treatment with a relaxing splint with retrusion control should be carried out in stages: the 1st month - relaxation, the second month - adaptation to anterior guidance, the 3rd month - elimination of the distal displacement of the lower jaw. The stability of the contacts on the tire is a confirmation of the harmonic function of the muscles of the maxillofacial region. Palpation of the masticatory muscles is an effective and accessible criterion for assessing their relaxation and comfortable position of the lower jaw.

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